

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND AI IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND COMMUNICATION

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Annotation. Year after year, many effective innovations are emerging in the field of education, especially in the process of language learning. One of them is artificial intelligence. This article is about the role of technological innovations and artificial intelligence in language learning and communication

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Technological innovations, especially artificial intelligences, are having a significant impact on language learning and communication. It is no secret that more students are interested in lessons that rely on modern technological innovations than traditional classes, and it has been proven that it is more effective to acquire knowledge in this way. This is because lessons organized with the help of artificial intelligence will be rich in the latest innovations, interesting, understandable and, most importantly, informative technologies.

“Traditional classroom-based teaching in which students are just passive recipients of information provided by a teacher has commonly been replaced. Living in the technological age, a wide range of tools which boost the effectiveness of second language teaching and help to avoid boredom and the routine of using only a coursebook can be observed in the classrooms”

Day by day, artificial intelligences bring various innovations and conveniences to the language learning process. As a result, there is a growing number of language learners. Different countries have started to use continuous technological innovation in the education process, and they state that such a change has had a positive impact on the education system. For example:

Estonia: The government of Estonia is one of the most advanced countries in the world when it comes to the digitalization of education. In this country, artificial intelligence and online platforms are widely used in the process of language learning. Specific applications for learning Estonian have been developed.

Sweden: Innovative methods of language learning are widely used in Sweden. For example, the Swedish government provides immigrants with a wide range of resources for learning a language, both online and through mobile apps.

China: In China, new technologies for language learning, particularly through mobile apps and online courses, users are offered materials in multiple languages. AI and VR technologies for language teaching are widely used in China.

United States: In the U.S., technological innovations in language learning are rampant in universities and schools, particularly on online learning platforms. Companies such as Duolingo and Babbel are popular in the U.S., taking an interactive approach to language teaching.

How does technological innovation contribute to language learning?

1. Modern mobile apps. For example: applications such as Duolingo, Busuu monitor and evaluate the learning of a language learner based on artificial intelligence. Each learner is provided with a personalised education and education plan according to his or her level. The reader will follow the course according to a plan tailored to him/her. In addition, he keeps track of how much time he practiced per day, how many new topics and words he learned.

They can reinforce the knowledge they have learned through interactive exercises and correct their mistakes. Online platforms such as Duolingo and Babbel play a major role in making learning a language extremely convenient. For example, with the Duolingo mobile app, users can explore many languages of the world.

2. Speakers. For example: Sites like Alexa or Chat gpt. Through them, language learners can develop their speaking skills through live communication, and at the same time, receive feedback and assessments that are relevant to their speech. Such artificial intelligences can talk to the reader on any level, on any topic. Their level of communication is almost equal to that of professionals. This makes the language learning process even more interesting. Some AI applications, such as conversational applications or chatbots, allow users to apply language in real-time practically. This allows you to develop the acquired language through practical exercises. AI language-learning apps are constantly updating their databases. At the same time, it allows you to get acquainted with new words, phrases and language changes, which will help you adapt the language to new trends and conditions.

3. The ability to search for information online. For example: artificial intelligences such as Luzia and Gemini. You can quickly find all kinds of information. One of the advantages is that a language learner doesn't waste time reading multiple sites or books to find information on a topic. It was just a matter of entering a topic, the necessary information will be found quickly.

4. Translation dictionaries. Artificial intelligence translation dictionaries and websites are not limited to just translating, they also provide you with synonyms, antonyms, and other forms of the same word.

Translation services such as Google Translate and DeepL are effective in language learning. Google Translate currently has the ability to translate in more than 100 languages, and this is a convenient tool for language learning. Such translators work very fast and are able to translate large volumes of text in a matter of seconds. This is very useful in cases where you need to save time and get quick results. You can get a translation anytime and anywhere using any device with an Internet connection. This makes it especially easy to work on mobile devices and other small platforms. AI translators are cheaper and more convenient than traditional translators, especially for small language learners or individual users. There is no need to pay translators, which is economically beneficial. AI translators are useful for people learning new languages. Translators help you quickly learn new words and phrases, as well as improve your grammar.

To conclude, technological innovations and artificial intelligence are expected to bring even greater changes in language learning in the coming years. These changes will undoubtedly help to make the educational process more effective and interesting. Thanks to artificial intelligence and advanced technology, language teaching will be further personalized, and learners are provided with exercises and materials according to their abilities. Through interactive platforms and real-time communication options, the possibility of learning a language quickly and efficiently increases. It is also important that new technologies help further develop language teaching equipment and facilitate language learning around the world. These changes will allow for a more effective and global expansion of the education system.

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